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ETHNOBOTANICAL DOCUMENTATION AND DIVERSITY ASSESSMENT OF MEDICINAL FLORA USED BY LOCAL INHABITANTS IN BAGABAG, NUEVA VIZCAYA

Proponents

Lead Researcher - Mrs. Cathelyn C. Mariano
Primary Collaborator - Mr. Olivar Reimos D. Barroga
Secondary Collaborator - Mr. Hansen T. Villanueva
Research Assistant - Jaryl Kate T. Dinamling

Abstract

This study documented and assessed the diversity of herbal medicines used in traditional therapies of local inhabitants in Sitio Masina, Brgy. Baretbet, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya. The ethnobotanical documentation was through field observation, semi-structured interviews, group discussions, and guided field walks. Use-value, informant consensus factor, and fidelity level of the identified species were quantified. Result of this endeavor may later benefit the community by informing them the benefits of the medicinal plants around that could help them cope up with their inabilities to get these from pharmacy and hospitals because of distance and lack of resources. Based on the survey, 31 medicinal plants with therapeutic purposes were identified by 22 local inhabitants. The plant with the highest Use Value (UV) was *Moringa oliefera (malunggay)*. It is regarded most important in treatment of wounds. In terms of Informant Consensus Factor (ICF), *Euphorbia hirta (tawa-tawa)* recorded the highest values. *Psidium guajava (bayabas)* was recorded with the highest Fidelity level (FL). The leaves were the most used part as infusion to cure different illnesses. Majority of the informants are familiar with the utilization, availability, importance, and perceived efficacy of these plants. Informants have a consensus for these plants that may be used for a particular disease category and each plant species mentioned has multiple uses. This study then provides a baseline data of plant diversity in Sitio Masina, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya and their medicinal uses can be used for the development of a compendium and will served as a basis for drug discovery to improve the utilization of herbal plants from national perspectives.

Keywords: fidelity level, *field observations*, informant consensus factor, *traditional medicines*, use-value

Introduction

The Philippines is one of the richest countries in the world in terms of biodiversity. As a megadiverse country, the various flora and fauna provides resources to meet basic needs for human survival, promotes economic development and offers environmental services. It cannot be denied that the rich biodiversity has provided millions of Filipinos resources and services especially for foods and medicines. Medicinal plants grow naturally around us. Over centuries, cultures worldwide have learned how to use plants to fight diseases and maintain health benefits. These available and culturally important traditional medicines form the basis of an accessible and affordable health care regime and are an essential source of livelihood for indigenous and rural populations (Awoyemi et al, 2012). People across the world use herbal medicines to treat various illnesses. Based on WHO, 2011, there are several scientific investigations on herbal plants have been initiated in many countries because of their contribution to the healthcare system. The study of medicinal plants and their use by indigenous healers is important for conserving cultural traditions and biodiversity and community healthcare, as well as drug development in the present and future.

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Medical ethnobotany—the study of medicinal plants by indigenous healers—is a discipline that has gained widespread attention across disciplines. The use of plant species as traditional medicines provides a real substitute in healthcare services for rural communities of the developing nations (Hayta, et al 2014). It has been estimated that around 80% of the population in developing countries depends on traditional medicines for primary health care system. These traditional medicines are cost-effective, safe and affordable (WHO 2002).

Iwu, 2022 defined and described ethnobotany as the study of interrelations between humans and plants; however, current use of the term implies the study of indigenous or traditional knowledge of plants. It involves the indigenous knowledge of plant classification, cultivation, and use as food, medicine and shelter. Although most of the early ethnobotanists studied plant used in cultures other than their own, the term ethnobotany does not necessarily mean the study of how 'other' people use plants. It is also not restricted to the study of medicinal plants by indigenous cultures. The use of ethnobotany in plant selection entails a careful recording of the relationship between indigenous communities and plants. It is a very complex undertaking that often requires collaboration of experts drawn from various disciplines such as anthropology, botany, ecology, pharmacy, linguistics, medicine and ethnography. Ethnobotany has now emerged as a discipline by itself that studies all types of interrelations between people and plants.

Baretbet is a barangay in the municipality of Bagabag, in the province of Nueva Vizcaya. The documentation of information on traditional herbal remedies is an important aspect of conservation approach in the community. This study documented the traditional knowledge of the local community on medicinal uses of surrounding plant diversity. This work, being the first collation and listing of all available data on medicinal plants in this area, will provide first ethnomedicinal and cultural assessment of flora found in the Municipality. The diversity of medicinal plant species and associated traditional knowledge is significant in primary health care system. Medicinal plant species with high RPL values should be screened for comprehensive phytochemical and pharmacological studies. This could be useful in novel drug discovery and to validate the ethnomedicinal knowledge.

In particular, there is a need for ethnobotanical documentation of native plants whose use was lost when Western culture swept in. This includes documenting wild foods that are still consumed by people today in a traditional manner but have been lost from their cultural context. Ethnobotanical studies can also be used to preserve knowledge about plants that were used in ceremonies or medicines by indigenous people but that are no longer used by them now that they live in modern society.

Documenting and assessing medicinal plants in a given community play significant roles in providing health care services to communities in far-flung, underserved areas. People from these areas also lack the means of transportation to even the closest rural health centers. The covid-19 pandemic also had unprecedented effects on the delivery of primary healthcare services. Identifying the medicinal flora in a given community fill the gaps in the healthcare system by bringing healthcare services like the provision of medical. These research is indeed community-based activity that target the socio-economically underserved communities.

In this light, this research, reached out the community in collaboration with the barangay councils of Sitio Masina, Baretbet, Bagabag. The community is known to be rich with flora and cultural diversity due to its geographic location. It is mountainous and abounds with water resources such as rivers, and natural springs, and waterfalls. Still, no comprehensive ethnobotanical studies have been carried out in the area except for the preliminary inventory of plants in different vegetation types by the residents. Therefore, preserving traditional knowledge and documentation of these herbal medicines is essential since both biological and cultural diversity face various threats. Thus, this

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study aims to document and assess the medicinal plants used by local inhabitants of the local folks in Sitio Masina. Result of this endeavor may later benefit the community by informing them the medicinal plants around that could help them cope up with their inabilities to get these from pharmacy and hospitals because of distance and lack of resources.

Conceptual and Analytical Framework

Last November 20, 2022, SMU LMCDAC together with the extension representatives from each department conducted a needs assessment studies at Sitio Masina, Baretbet, Bagabag. In the assessments, particular health conditions were reported such as, lack of: medical services , affordable medicines, long distance of health center; and lack of medical facilities/services for emergency cases. It has also been observed that the community has abundant plants however local folks are unaware of its medicinal or nutritional values.

This study shall be guided by the research paradigm presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researchers visited the BLGU, Baretbet, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya followed by an ocular visit to Sitio Masina. Field observation, interview, and informal focus group discussions were done. Informants were interviewed on an informal basis to maximize the source of information and understand the people's traditional medicinal system and its medicinal uses. The data gathered comprised local vernacular names, part(s) used, mode of preparation, diseases treated, route of application, and other uses of medicinal plants were compiled and summarized. All medicinal plants identified were photo-documented and initial identification were done during field walks with the local experts. This study provides baseline data of plant diversity in Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya and their medicinal uses can be used as a basis for drug discovery to improve the utilization of herbal plants from national perspectives.

Statement of Objectives

This study aimed to document and assess the ethnobotanical diversity of medicinal flora used by local inhabitants in Sitio Masina.

The following are the specific objectives:

1. To document the medicinal flora and traditional knowledge of local communities on indigenous plants used for medicinal purposes.
2. To compile data on traditional treatments against various ailments, including method of preparation, plant part(s) utilization and application;

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3. To assess the ethnomedicinal data using use value (UV), informant consensus factor (ICF), and fidelity level (FL) indices.

Methodology

A. Research Design

This study is a descriptive-quantitative type of research. Descriptive method was used to describe, identify and document medicinal flora and traditional knowledge of local communities on indigenous plants. Quantitative analysis was utilized to assess the ethnomedicinal data using, *use value (UV), informant consensus factor (ICF), and fidelity level (FL)* indices.

B. Research Locale

The study was conducted at Sitio Masina, Baretbet, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya. The area has a high number of endemic species, and the social importance of the medicinal plants in the community is essential for public health and the conservation of traditional knowledge.

C. Participants and Sample

The choice of the informants mainly included the member of the households, and older generations comprise of traditional healers, elderly age range from 20-70 years old, a long-time resident in the barangay, having a broader knowledge on the use of the plants as medicine or identified as a medicinal plant. A total of 31 participants were interviewed.

D. Instrument

Focus group interview was undertaken for three weeks. According to Ong et al. (2014), semi-structured interviews allow researchers to gather a great deal of data from a large number of people in a relatively short period while leaving the interviewee at ease to answer the questions put to them. This approach allowed flexibility in the conversations and open exchanges with the informants (Schultz et al. 2020).

An ethnobotanical survey was done through interviews using semi-structured questionnaires, observation, and focus group discussions with informants of the local community. The questionnaire guide was written in English and translated into Tagalog and Ilocano dialect. Demographic profile of informants, personal experiences or participation in the use and preparation of medicinal plants, part used, methods of preparation, modes of application and ethnomedicinal uses were documented. Informants were interviewed on an informal basis to maximize the source of information and understand the people's traditional medicinal system and its medicinal uses.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

Informants selection

The field surveys were undertaken for three (3) weeks. Before the conduct of the study, ethical approval from the SMU REB was secured. A communication letter was given to the Barangay Local Government Unit of Sitio Masina, Baretbet, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya. A group of informants were invited for a focus group discussion and interview.

Collection of Plant Specimen, Voucher Specimen Preparation, and Identification

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Collections of plant samples was conducted with the help of the informants on the identification of medicinal plants. Field works were done to collect information about the folk/culinary knowledge of medicinal plants used by the local inhabitants in Baretbet to cure various diseases. During field works, the forest guides and the local inhabitants, including older men and women familiar with the traditional use of collected plants, were interviewed. Standard taxonomical procedures were considered in gathering medicinal plants. Collected plants are pressed between newspapers treated with denatured alcohol and sandwiched in a wooden plant presser. This mounted specimen will later served as vouchers of medicinal plants with their taxonomic and ecological information. Voucher specimens were deposited at the UB 316. The Plant of the World (2019) served as the basis of the authenticity of the collected medicinal plants.

Treatment of Data

The documented and compiled data on the medicinal flora and traditional knowledge of local communities on indigenous plants was used as a basis on the development of a compendium. Ethnobotanical data was analyzed using quantitative tools such as use value (UV), informant consensus factor (ICF) fidelity level (FL) indices.

Furthermore, the three ethnobotanical indices were used to quantify the importance of medicinal plants: the use-value (UV), informant consensus factor (ICF), and fidelity level (FL). The UV was used to assess the relative importance of the species known locally using the formula: $UV = \Sigma U/n$, where U is the number of citations per species, and n is the total number of informants (Newman et al. 2012). To show the homogeneity of the information collected and the degree of overall agreement on the treatment of specific health disorders category was calculated using the formula of Informant Consensus Factor (Trotter et al. 1986). This quantitative method investigated the effectiveness of medicinal plants on particular ailments using the formula: $ICF = (N_{ur} - N_t)/(n_{ur}-1)$ where N_{ur} refers to the number of use citations in each category, N_t refers to the number of plant species used for a particular category by all informants.

Subsequently, the percentage of informants claiming the use of medicinal plants for similar major purposes were calculated for the most frequently reported diseases or ailments as follows: $FL (\%) = (N_p / N) \times 100$, N_p is the number of the informant that claim plant species to treat a particular disease, and N is the number of informants mentioned using the plants as a medicine to treat any given disease (Alexiades 1996).

Ethical Consideration Section

The field surveys were undertaken for three months, from January to March 2023. Before the conduct of the study, the researchers secured ethical approval to Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) with address and contact information at 2nd Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos; Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines (email: reb@smu.edu.ph; cellphone: 09177053041). An informed consent and informed permission were done through the Barangay Local Government Unit of Baretbet, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya. Likewise, acquired ethnobotanical information following the approved ethical standards.

The researchers declare no conflict of interest in the study because there is no personal benefit information, judgements or decisions in this research.

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All information gathered followed the Data Privacy Act where all data is protected be it private, personal or sensitive. The profiles of the informants and the data collected were treated with utmost confidentiality. The collected data were summarized and encoded in excel coded format. Only the researchers know the identity of the respondents. The accomplished questionnaires were retrieved only by the researchers and the identity of the informants was anonymized by a number code instead of their name. Except for the researchers, no one will be able to identify them as a respondent in the study. After the study is completed and finally presented, all the data in the research were stored in a password-protected zip file. The data was not distributed nor the identity of the informants reported to anyone. The results of this study is available for them if they ask to gain access.

The vulnerable populations of the study was not exploited. The researchers encouraged the vulnerable participants to make their own decisions and they were provided with informed consent. Their well-being and views, feelings and beliefs were also considered.

Since the study was face-to-face, there was minimal risk. But the researchers followed strictly the IATF protocols during the ocular inspection as well as during the interview proper. This study provided baseline data of plant diversity in Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya and their medicinal uses can be used as a basis for drug discovery to improve the utilization of herbal plants from national perspectives. Final output is the development of a compendium.

An informed consent was administered to allow the informants to review the purpose and requirements of the study. Upon agreeing, the interview part was done. The ICF contained statements ensuring confidentiality of shared information.

The intellectual property rights of the study are given to Saint Mary's University but the researchers will remain the authors.

Results and Discussions

Section 1-2. Documented and compiled data on medicinal flora, traditional knowledge, and traditional treatments.

A total of 31 plants as listed in Table 1 were documented. There plants are being used for medicinal purposes by the residents of Sitio Masina, Baretbet, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya.

Table 1: List of reported medicinal plants and their use-values and ailments treated				
Plant No.	Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Use Value (UV)	Ailments Treated
1	<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Dangla	0.27	Arm/Foot Injury /Colds/Malaria
2	<i>Origanum vulgare</i>	Oregano	0.23	Colds/Fever
3	<i>Malvaceae mallows</i>	Liplupiit	0.10	Arm/Foot Injury /Colds
4	<i>Asplenium nidus</i>	Kappa-Kappa	0.10	Colds/Flu

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5	<i>Tabernaemontana pandacaqui</i>	Kuribetbet	0.13	Rheumatism/Wound
6	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	Tanglad	0.17	UTI
7	<i>Annona muricata</i>	Guyabano	0.30	Stomach ache/ Diarrhea/body pain
8	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Baybas	0.30	Fever/ Stomach ache/Body pain
9	<i>Rhinacanthus nasutus</i>	Jasmin	0.10	Hypertension
10	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Tawa-tawa	0.10	Colds and Fever
11	<i>Cassia alata</i>	Andadasi	0.20	Skin disease/ Irritation
12	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Papaya	0.20	Diarrhea Dengue Fever
13	<i>Rauvolfia serpentina</i>	Serpentina	0.10	Diabetes/ Stomach ache/Body pain
14	<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Mamarem	0.10	Acute UTI
15	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Malunggay	0.40	Wound/ Stomach ache
16	<i>Ananas comosus</i>	Pinya	0.37	Hypertension
17	<i>Allium sativum L.</i>	Bawang	0.10	Colds/Flu
18	<i>Apium graveolens L.</i>	Kintsay	0.10	Hypertension
19	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus Lam.</i>	Langka	0.30	Diabetes
20	<i>Averrhoa bilimbi L.</i>	Kamias	0.13	Wound
21	<i>Basella alba L.</i>	Alugbati	0.23	Boils
22	<i>Blumea balsamifera</i>	Sambong	0.33	Diabetes/UTI/Cough/Fever/ body pain
23	<i>Citrus x macrocarpa Bunge</i>	Kalamansi	0.50	Cough/Flu
24	<i>Corchorus olitorius L.</i>	Saluyot	0.23	Sore throat/cold
25	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	Gumamela	0.20	boils
26	<i>Zingiber officinale Roscoe</i>	Luya	0.13	Sore throat/cold
27	<i>Sandoricum koetjape (Burm.f.) Merr.</i>	Santol	0.10	Skin rashes
28	<i>Muntingia calabura L.</i>	Aratiles	0.13	Diarrhea
29	<i>Momordica charantia L.</i>	Ampalaya	0.17	Diabetes
30	<i>Mimosa pudica L.</i>	Makahiya	0.10	Asthma/Wound/Fever
31	<i>Mangifera indica L.</i>	Mangga	0.10	Diabetes

Table 1 summarizes the reported medicinal plants and their use-reports, use values, and ailments treated. Moreover, there are 31 plant species identified by the informants as therapeutic. Furthermore, most plant species mentioned have high use-value, indicating that most of the informants are familiar with the utilization, availability, importance, and perceived efficacy of these plants for medicinal purposes. Specifically, the following plants having the highest use-value (UV) were, *Citrus x macrocarpa Bunge* (UV=0.50), *Moringa oleifera* (UV=0.40), *Ananas comosus* (UV=0.37), *Blumea balsamifera* (UV=0.33), *Artocarpus heterophyllus Lam.* (UV=0.30), *Annona muricata* (UV=0.30), *Psidium guajava* (UV=0.30), *Vitex negundo* (UV=0.27), *Origanum vulgare* (UV=0.23),

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Basella alba L. (UV=0.23), *Corchorus olitorius L.* (UV=0.23), *Cassia alata* (UV=0.20), *Carica papaya* (UV=0.20), *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* (UV=0.20), *Cymbopogon citratus* (UV=0.17), and *Momordica charantia L.* (UV=0.17).

This result is supported by several studies, including the study of Dapar et al. and Abe and Otani, where *C. papaya*, *H. rosa-sinensis*, *C. alata*, and *M. oleifera* have high UV. Since it has high UV, this indicates a possible high harvesting pressure, these medicinal plants need to be conserved for continued therapeutic use and likely scientific studies in the future.

Morover, there were spotted plants in the community but the informants are not aware of their benefits.

Section 3. Ethnomedicinal data using use value (UV), informant consensus factor (ICF), and fidelity level (FL) indices.

The table below presents the eight (8) different categories of the reported ailments, namely: I (Certain Infectious and Parasitic Diseases): Diarrhea, Malaria, Acute UTI; IV (Endocrine, Nutritional, and Metabolic Diseases) Diabetes; IX (Diseases of the Circulatory System): Rheumatism, Hypertension X (Diseases of the Respiratory System): Sore throat, Colds, Flu, and Dengue Fever; XII (Diseases of the skin and subcutaneous tissue): Skin Irritation/ Skin disease; Boils; XVIII (Symptoms, signs, and abnormal clinical and laboratory findings not elsewhere classified): Body Pain, Stomach ache; XIX (Injury, poisoning, and certain other consequences of external cause): Arm or foot Injury; and XX (External Causes of Morbidity and Mortality): Wound Infection.

Table 2: Fidelity Level (FL) and informant consensus factor (ICF) to identify the most frequently used species in each ailment

Disease Category According to ICD-10	Disease	No. of Use-Reports	No. of Plants Used	ICF	Most Frequently Used Species	FL in this Category (%)
I. Certain Infectious and Parasitic Diseases	Diarrhea Malaria Acute UTI	48	9	0.76	<i>Blumea balsamifera</i>	24.00
IV. Endocrine, Nutritional, and Metabolic Diseases	Diabetes	21	3	0.90	<i>Rauvolfia serpentina</i>	10.50
IX. Diseases of the Circulatory System	Rheumatism; Hypertension	34	3	0.85	<i>Ananas comosus</i>	17.00
X. Diseases of the Respiratory System	Sore throat, Colds, Flu, and Dengue Fever	50	7	0.79	<i>Vitex negundo</i>	25.00

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XII. Diseases of the skin and subcutaneous tissue	Skin Irritation/ Skin disease; Boils	1	1	-	-	-
XVIII. Symptoms, signs, and abnormal clinical and laboratory findings not elsewhere classified	Body Pain; Stomach ache	17	10	0.43	<i>Annona muricata</i>	8.50
XIX. Injury, poisoning, and certain other consequences of external cause	Arm or foot Injury	18	3	0.88	<i>Malvaceae mallows</i>	9.00
XX. External Causes of Morbidity and Mortality	Wound Infection	11	2	0.90	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	5.50

Note: The reported ailments of the documented medicinal plants above were categorized based on the International Classification of Disease (ICD-10) version 2019.

Table 2 summarizes the fidelity level (FL) and informant consensus factor (ICF) to identify each ailment's most frequently used species. Most plants have low FL (values far from 100%), indicating that each plant species mentioned has multiple uses. Moreover, *R. serpentina* and *M. oleifera* have the highest ICF value (ICF=0.90) in categories IV and XX, while *A. muricata* has the lowest ICF (ICF=0.43) in category XVIII. The high ICF value indicates that the informants have a consensus for these plants that may be used for a particular disease category. However, the low ICF value suggests an insufficient consensus among informants on using a plant species to address this disease category.

As compared with commercial medicines that provide modern alternatives to herbal medicine, a low ICF value reflects the reduced use of some traditional remedies. However, ICF values may vary from culture to culture, reflecting the differences in medicinal plants found and used in their particular community and the ailments for which these plants are being used. For instance, the study of Tantengco et al., in Bataan had the highest ICF value for the 'disease of the eye and the adnexa' and for the 'diseases during the postpartum period.'

Conclusions:

This study confirms that plants are still valued for their therapeutic purposes by the local folks in Sitio Masina, Baretbet, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya, given the fact that they have difficult access to traditional modern health facilities because of the distance to the government clinics and hospitals. The number of species and diversity of plants in the community paved the way for the conduct of an ethnobotanical assessment which revealed the use values, consensus factors and fidelity levels of the 31 documented and collected plants, excluding other plant species which they did not name because they are unaware of the medicinal uses of those plants. This documentation of ethnomedicinal plants showed the

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prevailing ethnobotanical knowledge on the traditional uses of plants-based medicine in treating certain diseases and health problems among the local inhabitants. Majority of the informants are familiar with the utilization, availability, importance, and perceived efficacy of these plants. Informants have a consensus for these plants that may be used for a particular disease category and each plant species mentioned has multiple uses. The significance of this ethnobotanical knowledge has furnished novel information which could provide a basis for new avenues in the future development of compendium and to educate the inhabitants in improving the utilization of herbal plants within their local community.

Recommendations:

1. Expand the study to a bigger community or municipalities in-order to document more endemic plant species and higher number of informants.
2. The data from this study can be disseminated to the Brgy. Captain and the local officials which would serve as their basis for conserving their biological resources specifically the medicinal plants.
3. Extensive research is encouraged to continue exploring medicinal plants' potentials to treat various illnesses against expensive medicines.
4. To develop a compendium or a catalogue which could serve as basis in the formulation of products that can be utilized by the community.

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Appendices

Photo-documentations

Courtesy call to the Brgy Captain and local officials

Collection of medicinal plants

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Interview with the informants

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